

Multivariant Assessment of Physicochemical Characteristics of Kottakayal Wetland in South India: A Pilot Study on Degraded Ecosystem Under the Threat of Sand and Clay Mining

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Abstract- Water is a crucial natural resource, and its quality is defined by its physical, chemical, and biological properties. The present study investigates the physico-chemical properties of the Kottakayal wetland, located in the Ithikkara block, South India, and explores its ecological aspects. Six sampling sites were selected to evaluate parameters such as temperature, pH, transparency, carbon dioxide, dissolved oxygen, salinity, chloride, total solids (TS), total suspended solid (TSS), total dissolved solids (TDS), Total alkalinity, total hardness, calcium hardness, magnesium hardness, nitrite, phosphate and silicate. The study reveals significant fluctuations and interdependencies among these parameters, impacting the wetland's ecological status. Multivariant analysis reveals the distinguishing nature of the study sites selected for analysis. The findings indicate that while most parameters remain within permissible limits, the high chloride concentration renders the water unsuitable for drinking and irrigation purposes. However, the water quality is deemed suitable for fish culture, highlighting the need for sustainable water management practices to protect this valuable ecosystem.

Keywords- Wetland, physico-chemical properties, multivariant analysis, chloride concentration, ecological assessment, sustainable water management, fish culture.

I INTRODUCTION

The most abundant natural resource available to mankind is water. Quality of water is determined by its physical, chemical and biological components. Majority of our fresh water bodies are polluted thereby decreasing water potability. The key issue in several developing countries in the present scenario is the availability of clean and potable water. Growth of cities and towns is determined by the availability of safe and potable water. Population growth and economic development have put India into a situation of scarcity of natural resources, especially water resource. The Knowledge of the role played by water in sustaining life and the need to conserve it are being realized globally [1].

Physico-chemical parameters determine the abundance and diversity of a lake. To fully assess an ecosystem both biological and physico-chemical studies are to be performed. Knowledge of physico-chemical properties is inevitable especially in studies related to nutrient dynamics, energy transfer, standing stock and productivity of an aquatic ecosystem. Seasonal fluctuations and interdependency of physico-chemical parameters are well evident in all the hydro-biological studies. An attempt has been made in this research article to unravel the physico-chemical properties of the wetland and its interactions.

This study provides a baseline understanding of the transformation and degradation processes affecting the Kottakayal wetland ecosystem. This ecosystem is undergoing significant ecological changes as it is evolving from a former paddy field to a water body. Human endeavours like sand and clay mining

have been instrumental for these ecological changes. By examining the current physico-chemical properties and ecological conditions, this pilot study offers valuable insights into the ongoing degradation and potential pathways for restoration. Furthermore, the study contributes to the understanding of how abandoned agricultural lands can change into aquatic ecosystems, highlighting the impacts of such changes on local biodiversity, water quality, and ecosystem services. It can also inform future conservation efforts and policy-making by identifying critical areas for intervention and sustainable management practices to mitigate the adverse effects of human activities

II MATERIAL AND METHODS

A. Study Area

Kottakayal lies in Grid no. 58D/09 of Survey of India Toposheet, between 8°51'35.236" to 8°54'11.144" North Latitude and 76°40'31.547" to 76°43'4.784" East longitude near Pallimon-Ithikkara confluence. Kottakayal has an area of 2.32 Km². It flows through Adichanalloor, Thrikovilvattom and Nedumpana panchayats. Kottakayal belongs to Ithikkara block. As Kottakayal is situated at low lying area the chances of ecological degradation is fairly high. 1967 SOI toposheet reveals that the water body now known as Kottakayal was cropland especially paddy field. This particular grid area was constituted by 1.96 km² of Cropland (paddy), 0.15 km² of mixed crops, 0.10 km² of river/stream and 0.11 km² of water-logged area (table I). As per the 2018 satellite images this entire area is water logged which is now known as Kottakayal (Fig1). Land cover classification of Kottakayal was done using ESRI's ArcGIS 10.3 software. Sand and clay mining predominant in this area has alchemized these paddy fields to water logged area. More over the entire land was debilitated for any sort of cultivation due to intrusion of saline water from the Ithikkara River to the great pits that were the outcome of indiscriminate and unethical sand and clay mining.

TABLE I: LAND COVER DIFFERENCE OF KOTTAKAYAL REGION

Land cover	1967(SOI Topo)	2018(Landsat)
Cropland (Paddy)	1.96 km ²	Converted to Kottakayal
Mixed crops	0.15 km ²	
River/ Stream	0.10 km ²	
Waterlogged	0.11 km ²	
Total	2.32 km ²	2.32 km ²

The present investigation is designed to analyses the various ecological aspects of this water body. Six sampling stations were selected (Fig 1). Sites 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 are located to the south of Kundumon Bridge whereas site 6 is to the north of Kundumon Bridge. Sampling sites were fixed in such a way that they were almost 1 km apart from one another. Site 1 is the region where Kottakayal joins with Ithikkara River, Site 2 was selected due to its peculiar topographical feature that was more like a gulf in its appearance. Site 4 and site 5 were the active sites of clay and sand mining. Site 5 is located close to the

crusher unit of M-sand factory. Mining also prevailed at site 3 but it was not as much as it was at site 4 and site 5. Site 6 was located on the opposite side of the Kundumon Bridge which was having a comparatively higher elevation than the other sites selected for the study. There was a small embankment below the Kundumon Bridge, which was constructed to prevent the inflow of saline water from Ithikkara River during high tides.

FIG: 1 LOCATION OF SAMPLING STATIONS LABELLED 1 TO 6

B. Sample Collection

Sample were collected during the months July to November 2020 in high density polyethylene (HDPE) bottles that had been prewashed three times with water sample before collection and properly sealed. Samples for cation analysis were acidified using 2M HNO₃. Then the samples were transferred to the laboratory and evaluated for various physicochemical parameters following analytical protocols of [2]. Physical parameters such as temperature, pH, transparency, carbon dioxide, dissolved oxygen, salinity, chloride, total solids (TS), total suspended solid (TSS), total dissolved solids (TDS), Total alkalinity, total hardness, calcium hardness, magnesium hardness, nitrite, phosphate and silicate were evaluated. Temperature was measured on site itself using mercury thermometer with $\pm 0.01^{\circ}\text{C}$ accuracy. pH of was

measured with an electronic portable pH meter. Secchi disc of diameter 20 cm was used for measuring transparency [3]. TDS and TSS were separated by filtering the water sample through a 0.45 μ m filter paper and determined according to standard procedure[2]. Total alkalinity was determined by titration method using 0.02 N standard sulphuric acid as titrant and phenolphthalin, methyl orange as indicators. Chloride was determined by titration method using 0.014 N Silver nitrate as titrant and potassium chromate as indicator. The total hardness of water was determined by EDTA titrimetric method. Calcium hardness was determined by titrating water samples with EDTA using murexide indicator[2]. Nitrite, phosphate and silicate were measured using Brucine method, stannous chloride, ammonium molybdate method respectively using UV visible spectrometer. Salinity of water was measured using EUTECH PC2700 multi parameter testing instrument.

C. Statistical analysis

Descriptive statistics like mean and standard deviation was calculated using MS Excel Software. Correlation analysis and multivariant analysis was done using Past 4.03.

III RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of physicochemical parameters of Kottakayal are given in table II. Water temperature is an important factor in an aquatic ecosystem because it influences the physicochemical properties of water and the life it supports[4]. Water temperature ranged from 24° C to 27°C with an average of 25.5 \pm 1.04. Shallow water bodies show greater fluctuation in water temperature with changing atmospheric temperature [5]. Alterations in pH of a water body is accompanied by alterations in other physico-chemical properties [6]. pH values in a water body are influenced by removal of carbon dioxide by photosynthesis through bicarbonate degradation, fresh water influx, reduction of salinity and temperature and decomposition of organic matter [7]. High pH values promote algal growth and results in the bloom of phytoplankton [8]. pH values ranged from 6.7 to 7 with an average of 6.93 \pm 0.12. The [9] permissible limit of pH is 6.5 to 8.5. pH values were within these limits. pH ranging from 6 to 9 is most suitable for pond fish culture. Values of pH above 9 are unfit for living organisms [10].

Transparency of the water body regulates the energy relationship at various trophic levels. Penetration of light in a standing water column depends on transparency. Transparency is dependent on turbidity which is directly related to the amount of particulate matter suspended in it. Hence both transparency and turbidity play a valuable role in the energy changes in an aquatic ecosystem [11]. Transparency in Kottakayal ranged from 74 cm to 167.5 cm with an average value of 119.33 \pm 34.95. TDS are the solids in water that are in dissolved state. Carbonates and bicarbonates of calcium, magnesium, sodium, potassium, iron and manganese mainly contributes to the dissolved solids in an aquatic ecosystem. TDS signifies the various minerals constituted in the water body. Increase in TDS increases the nutrient status of a water body, which would result in eutrophication [8], [12]. TDS ranged from 0.3 mg l⁻¹ to 3.2 mg l⁻¹. Higher TDS increases turbidity which in turn decreases light penetration thereby affecting

photosynthesis and finally the productivity of the ecosystem. High TDS reduces solubility of gases like oxygen and make water unfit for drinking and enhances eutrophication of lakes [13]. Wetlands are sinks for deposition of nutrients [14]. TDS values of Kottakayal were within the BIS permissible limits of 500 mg l⁻¹. This shows that the water can be used for drinking and agriculture purpose.

TABLE II
CONCENTRATION OF DIFFERENT PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PARAMETERS OF KOTTAKAYAL

Parameters	Maximum	Minimum	Mean	SD
Water Temp. (°C)	27	24	25.5	1.04
Transparency(cm)	167.5	74	119.33	34.95
TDS (mg/L)	3.2	0.3	1.78	1.07
TSS (mg/L)	5.6	0.1	2.48	2.49
TS (mg/L)	8.8	0.4	4.26	2.94
pH	7	6.7	6.93	0.12
Free CO ₂ (mg/L)	7.6	6.68	7.11	0.29
DO (mg/L)	6.88	5.65	6.02	0.43
Total alkal.(mg/L)	40	20	30	6.32
Ca hard.(mg/L)	7.21	2.2	4.47	2.25
Mg hard.(mg/L)	5.2	0.49	3.14	1.82
Chloride (mg/L)	164.72	26.98	90.88	50.56
Salinity (ppt)	0.32	0.08	0.19	0.08
Nitrite (mg/L)	0.0064	0.0028	0.0034	0.0015
Phosphate (mg/L)	0.62	0.01	0.07	0.23
Silicate (mg/L)	3.73	1.16	2.26	1.04

TSS ranged from 0.1 mg l⁻¹ to 5.6 mg l⁻¹. Increased turbidity, low photosynthetic rate, rise in water temperature and decrease in dissolved oxygen are the results of high TSS in water [15]. TSS values were within the BIS permissible limit for drinking and agricultural use. Total solids demonstrate the chemical status of the lake and are initiators of edaphic relations that constitutes lake productivity [16]. TS ranged from 0.4 mg l⁻¹ to 8.8 mg l⁻¹.

Free carbon dioxide is the source of carbon that can be assimilated and incorporated into the aquatic autotrophs. Free carbon dioxide is directly proportional to bicarbonates and inversely proportional to carbonates. Less values of free carbon dioxide during post-monsoon may be due to high photosynthetic activity utilizing this free carbon dioxide [17]. Free carbon dioxide ranged from 6.68 mg l⁻¹ to 7.6 mg l⁻¹. Dissolved oxygen, being a major component of the aquatic ecosystem, defines the water quality and the life supported by the ecosystem [18]. DO values ranged from 5.65 mg l⁻¹ to 6.88 mg l⁻¹. In a natural water body alkalinity is the function of bicarbonates and carbonates. Salts of these carbonates and bicarbonates get hydrolyzed in solution to produce hydroxyl ions. Alkalinity increases due to increase in carbonates and bicarbonates caused by the degradation of plants and other organisms and organic waste in the water body [8], [19]. Total alkalinity ranged from 20 mg l⁻¹ to 40 mg l⁻¹. Total alkalinity was within [9] permissible limit of 600 mg l⁻¹.

The ecological significance of calcium and magnesium in an aquatic habitat is a well-established fact. Calcium is an essential micronutrient in an aquatic ecosystem whose concentration varies with the influx of materials present in the system. Calcium hardness increases during pre-monsoon due to rapid evaporation, oxidation and decomposition of organic matter [20]. Calcium hardness ranged from 2.2 mg l⁻¹ to 7.2 mg l⁻¹. Calcium hardness was within [9] permissible limit of 200 mg l⁻¹. Calcium is an important element that influences the flora of an ecosystem. It plays a vital role in metabolism and growth of organisms

Magnesium is essential for biosynthesis of chlorophyll and enzymatic transformations, particularly for photosynthesis in algae, fungi and bacteria. Higher the concentration of magnesium, higher the total hardness [21]. According to (Shruthi and Rajashekhar, 2013), leaching of rocks and exoskeleton of arthropods as well as shells of molluscs are the main sources of calcium and magnesium. Magnesium hardness ranged from 0.49 mg l⁻¹ to 5.2 mg l⁻¹. Magnesium hardness was within the [9] permissible limit of 100 mg l⁻¹. (Murhekar, 2011) commented that magnesium is directly related to hardness and concentration of magnesium is usually lower than calcium in water bodies. Magnesium acts as a limiting factor for phytoplankton growth by playing a vital role in chlorophyll biosynthesis [24].

Chloride ions are among the major inorganic ions in water [25]. Industrial effluents, sewages and irrigation wastes are the major contributors of chloride ions in a fresh water ecosystem. High chloride concentration is an indication of organic pollution mainly of animal origin. Increase in temperature, low water levels and sewage mixing bring about rise in chloride levels in water bodies [26]. Chloride ranged from 26.98 mg l⁻¹ to 164.72 mg l⁻¹. The BIS permissible limit of chloride is 1000 mg l⁻¹. Water becomes unsuitable for human consumption when chloride is above 200 mg l⁻¹ [27]. Intrusion of salt water from Ithikkara River might be responsible for more chloride during the period. Sand and clay mining was predominant in this area during the course of study.

Sand mining along Kerala's coast has intensified since the 1990s, which has strained the freshwater resources and increased their vulnerability to saltwater intrusion. The natural deposition of sediments which is significant for maintaining the balance between freshwater and saline environment is disrupted by extraction activities[28]. Sand mining in Kadalundi river basin has led to salt water intrusion affecting coastal aquifers up to 1.9 km from the coast [29]. Extensive sand and clay mining in Shasthamkotta fresh water lake has led to saline water intrusion disrupting the natural habitat [30]. Distribution of living organisms in an aquatic ecosystem is regulated by salinity which is one of the important water quality parameters [31]. Salinity ranged from 0.08 ppt to 0.32 ppt.

Nitrite is the partially oxidized form of nitrogen and is found in low concentration than nitrate. It is formed as a result of bacterial action either through heterotrophic oxidation of ammonia to nitrite or by the reduction of nitrate [32]. Nitrite ranged from 0.0028 mg l⁻¹ to 0.0064 mg l⁻¹. Rain water, soil organic matter and other organic substances are the origin of nitrogen compounds in fresh water [33].

Phosphate is the prime nutrient causing eutrophication of water bodies which results in algal blooming. Release of phosphate from the bottom sediments and the organic load of the water body enhance the growth of weeds and phytoplankton in lakes [8], [34], [35]. The primary productivity of an aquatic ecosystem is greatly influenced by its phosphate content, since it limits phytoplankton production and regulates the growth of organisms [36]. Phosphate ranged from 0.009 mg l⁻¹ to 0.6269 mg l⁻¹. Utilization of phosphate by photoautotrophs and the buffering process of sediments under changing environmental conditions may be the cause of low phosphate concentration during the hot months [37].

TABLE III
CORRELATION COEFFICIENT BETWEEN DIFFERENT HYDROCHEMICAL PARAMETERS OF KOTTAKAYAL

	Temp	TS	pH	Free CO2	DO	TL. Alk	Ca Hd	Mg Hd	Chloride	Salinity	Nitrite	Phosphate
Temp	1											
TS	0.3366	1										
pH	0.6298	0.727	1									
Free CO2	0.2353	-0.2713	-0.121	1								
DO	-0.845*	-0.6340	-0.926*	0.028	1							
TL. Alk	-0.603*	-0.2147	0.021	-0.042	0.232	1						
Ca Hd	0.3168	-0.5341	-0.443	-0.007	0.131	-0.61	1					
Mg Hd	0.235	-0.5154	-0.381	-0.253	0.104	-0.478	0.957	1				
Chloride	0.310	-0.4313	-0.310	-0.168	-0.019	-0.417	0.901	0.94	1			
Salinity	0.3238	-0.4121	-0.299	-0.167	-0.034	-0.429	0.898*	0.93*	0.99*	1		
Nitrite	0.698*	0.1885	0.250	0.489	-0.363	-0.750	0.269	0.054	-0.039	-0.031	1	
Phosphate	-0.233	-0.1224	0.363	-0.159	-0.120	0.818*	-0.51	-0.34	-0.387	-0.401	-0.44	1

*Correlation is significant at $p > 0.05$ (two-tailed test)

Physical mixing of sea water with fresh water, adsorption on sediment particles, interaction between chemicals and minerals, co-precipitation with humic components and biological removal by phytoplankton especially diatoms and silico-flagellates are responsible for the varying silicate concentration in an aquatic ecosystem [38]. Silicate exists universally both in ionic and colloidal forms in a natural water body. Diatoms use silicate for building up their frustules (shell wall). Availability of silica has a strong influence on succession and productivity of an aquatic ecosystem [39]. Silicate content ranged from 1.16 mg l⁻¹ to 3.73 mg l⁻¹.

The physico-chemical parameters of Kottakayal were within the BIS limit of tolerance except for chloride, which makes the water body unsuitable for drinking and irrigation purpose. Physico-chemical characteristics of Kottakayal is suitable for fish culture. Table III shows the correlation matrix of different physico-chemical parameters of Kottakayal. Dissolved oxygen and temperature show high negative correlation (-0.845). This was in accordance with the results obtained by [40], [41]. Dissolved oxygen showed high negative correlation (-0.926) with pH of the water. Total alkalinity showed negative correlation with temperature (-0.603). Similar results were obtained by [42]. Positive correlation was obtained between temperature and nitrite (0.698). There was high positive correlation between salinity,

calcium hardness, magnesium hardness and salinity. Total alkalinity showed strong positive correlation with phosphate (0.818).

Multivariant Analysis- Principal Component analysis (PCA)

Principal component analysis envisages the strength of correlations and covariance in the data [43]. The studies on the application of factor analysis in the assessment of ground water quality in black foot disease in Taiwan has inferred the factor loading value in the range 0.30-0.50 as weak, 0.05-0.075 moderate and > 0.75 as strong [44].

FIG 2 SCREEN PLOT OF PCA

FIG 3 LOADING PLOT OF PC 1

FIG 4 LOADING PLOT OF PC 2

FIG 5 LOADING PLOT OF PC 3

The elbow of the screen plot (fig 2) appears around the second or third component of PCA, suggesting that the first three components capture majority of the meaningful variance in the dataset. Hence PC1, PC2 and PC3 are considered in this study. Loading plot of principal component analysis reveals the correlation between the original variables and the principal components. X-axis of the loading plot represents the original variables of the dataset. Y-axis represents the correlation coefficient between

the original variables and the principal components. The values range from -1 to 1. Values closer to 1 or -1 indicates strong correlation whereas values close to 0 indicates weak or no correlation. Transparency, calcium hardness, magnesium hardness, chloride, salinity and silicate show strong positive correlation with PC1. Whereas TDS, TSS, TS, pH, total hardness and phosphate show strong negative correlation with PC1 (fig 3).

Temperature, TSS, TS and nitrite show strong positive correlation with PC2. Factors such as dissolved oxygen, total alkalinity and phosphate exhibit strong negative correlation with PC2 (fig 4). Loading plot of PC3 explains strong positive correlation of TDS with PC3 and strong negative correlation of free carbon dioxide with PC3 (fig 5).

Factor loading for different parameters at Kottakayal is given in table IV. PC1 marked 45.159% of variance in data. PC2 represents 23.152% variance in data set and PC 3 represents 15.094% variance in data set. PC1 indicated strong positive loading for transparency (0.886), calcium hardness (0.913), magnesium hardness (0.822), chloride (0.770), salinity (0.763), and silicate (0.902). PC1 indicated low positive loading for dissolved oxygen (0.468). The PC 2 inferred strong positive loading for temperature (0.853) and nitrite (0.780). Moderate loading was shown by TSS (0.705), TS (0.579) and pH (0.504). Whereas PC3 had moderate positive loading for TDS (0.670), magnesium hardness (0.529), chloride (0.569), salinity (0.568) and weak positive correlation for total hardness (0.492).

TABLE IV
FACTOR LOADING FOR DIFFERENT PARAMETERS AT KOTTAKAYAL

	PC 1	PC 2	PC 3
Temperature	0.017	0.853	0.143
Transparency	0.886	-0.365	-0.143
TDS	-0.688	-0.049	0.670
TSS	-0.567	0.705	-0.222
TS	-0.730	0.579	0.055
pH	-0.743	0.504	0.249
Free CO ₂	0.194	0.076	-0.775
DO	0.468	-0.683	-0.328
Total Alkalinity	-0.451	-0.850	0.059
Total Hardness	-0.766	-0.318	0.492
Calcium Hardness	0.913	0.268	0.282
Magnesium Hardness	0.822	0.153	0.529
Chloride	0.770	0.179	0.569
Salinity	0.763	0.197	0.568
Nitrite	0.161	0.780	-0.468
Nitrate	0.234	-0.210	-0.124
Phosphate	-0.541	-0.568	0.243
Silicate	0.902	0.071	0.065
Eigenvalue	8.580	4.398	2.867
% variance	45.159	23.152	15.094

Station 1 is highly separated from other stations as indicated in the biplot (fig 6). This indicates the unique characters of station 1 based on the physico-chemical parameters measured. Variables such as transparency, TDS, TS, pH, calcium hardness, magnesium hardness, chloride, salinity, and silicate contribute to PC1. Station 1 is far along component 2 which suggests distinct profile based on variables contributing to component 2. This station is influenced by higher levels of nitrite, salinity, calcium hardness and magnesium hardness. The unique profile of station 1 can be attributed to higher values in the variables that strongly contribute to component 2. This could be due to hydrological influences of Ithikkara River. Station 1 is the region where a tributary of Ithikkara River joins Kottakayal.

FIG 6 BIPLLOT OF PRINCIPAL COMPONENT ANALYSIS (PCA)- COMPONENT 1 VERSUS 2

Station 5 lie far along component 1, which indicates that it has distinct values in variables contributing strongly to component 1. Higher values of dissolved oxygen, transparency and total alkalinity influences the unique profile of station 5. Station 2 is highly influenced by parameters like calcium hardness, nitrite, salinity, silicate, chloride and magnesium hardness. Station 4 is greatly influenced by parameters such as TDS, phosphate and total alkalinity.

Station 3 and 6 lie close to each other on the biplot (fig 6). This indicates that these two sampling stations have similar profile in terms of the measured variables. Hydrochemical parameters like pH, TSS, TS and free carbon dioxide are the major influencing factors in station 3 and 6.

IV CONCLUSION

The study of the physico-chemical properties of the Kottakayal wetland in South India has provided valuable insights into the ecological status and water quality of the region. The analysis of various parameters, including temperature, pH, dissolved oxygen, free carbon dioxide, salinity, and total

dissolved solids, total solids, total suspended solids, nutrients, chloride, total hardness, calcium hardness, magnesium hardness and transparency revealed notable spatial variations and interdependencies that influence the overall health of the wetland ecosystem. While most of the measured parameters remain within acceptable limits, the elevated chloride concentration is a concern, rendering the water unsuitable for drinking and irrigation purposes. Nevertheless, the water quality supports fish culture, suggesting its potential for aquaculture activities. The findings underline the importance of continuous monitoring and sustainable management practices to maintain the ecological balance and ensure the long-term viability of the Kottakayal. Future efforts should focus on mitigating the factors contributing to the high chloride levels and enhancing the wetland's resilience against environmental stressors. To conserve Kottakayal wetland ecosystem and mitigate the impact of clay and sand mining the following recommendations can be considered.

RECOMENDATIONS

- Law and rules formulated to check encroachment of wetlands for settlement and infrastructure development should be strictly enacted.
- Scientific analysis of the mining sites should be made before allowing small and large scale sand and clay mining. Mining should be banned in the areas that are ecologically sensitive.
- Measures should be taken to update resources, technologies, database and management regarding mining activities in wetlands and their restoration and management. For these researches and developmental activities should be strengthened.
- Village watch groups and clusters should be set up to guard mining areas so as to check the intrusion of illegal miners. Only licensed miners should have access to mining sites.
- Encourage the use of alternatives to sand and clay for construction purposes and for brick and tile making. Alternative building technologies where the use of river sand is low or mere minimum should be devised and promoted.
- There should be proper scientific methods to reclaim the abandoned mine pits.
- Sand and clay mining should be prohibited in areas where small landholders are settled.
- Strict guidelines should be formulated and followed to allow sand and clay extraction from specific areas.
- Proper measures should be taken to check that mining activities do not progress beyond the depth of water table of adjoining areas.
- Strict enforcement of all the laws pertaining to the conservation of wetlands should be done without fail.

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